

Transition between deformation modes of a buckled beam using piezoelectric actuators

Taha Ajnada^[0000-0002-9172-8050], Christophe Giraud-Audine^[0000-0003-3461-0328],
Frédéric Giraud^[0000-0002-5688-711X], and Betty Lemaire-Semail^[0000-0002-4157-6976]

Univ. Lille, Arts et Metiers Institute of Technology, Centrale Lille, Junia, ULR 2697 - L2EP,
F-59000 Lille, France

Abstract. As an application to haptic feedback, this paper presents the dynamic snap-through of a pre-buckled bistable system using piezoelectric actuators. It can be used on a car's modular dashboard, with buttons that appear and disappear depending on the driver's condition or abilities. It can also be used for push buttons with variable stiffness. The proof of concept for such a system, with quasi-static excitation of the piezoelectric actuators, has already been demonstrated. Exciting the actuators according to one of the vibration modes to achieve snap-through will be presented. The use of this principle for haptics is new. The benefit of triggering the snap through thanks to vibration is to reduce the required voltage by a factor of ten over static voltage. That is particularly important in applications such as haptics, where the source voltage level is small. It is demonstrated as a preliminary study using a finite element simulation. We will show that, for example, a centimetre-scale aluminium beam, buckled with an initial transverse displacement of about 1 mm, can be switched with a few tens of volts using a piezoelectric patch. A comparison will be made between the static and dynamic voltage thresholds for snap-through, by varying the position of the piezoelectric actuator.

Keywords: Bistable beam · Snap-through · Dynamic actuation.

1 Introduction

Bistable systems have two stable equilibrium states, separated by an unstable equilibrium position [1]. They can switch from an up-position to a down-position, and vice-versa. This tilts are called snap-through and snap-back respectively [2, 3]. It takes place under the application of an external force.

We aim in this paper to switch a pre-stressed bistable beam using a vibrating electro-active material. The piezoelectric (PZ) materials offer a good controllability with very fast response times. Besides, the electromechanical conversion is increasingly improved nowadays [4]. Here we are studying an aluminium structure to which a PZ actuator is bonded. The system is initially pre-compressed until it buckles. The initial centre deflection is 1 mm. The main advantage of this approach is to create large displacements (due to buckling) from small piezoelectric strains. The actuator operates the bistable system, which snaps from one stable state to another [5, 6].

This paper investigates the design of a bistable system actuated by PZ actuators excited at specific frequencies. In a first part, we present the buckled structure with its bonded actuator. Then, the snap-through under the PZ dynamic actuation will be simulated using finite element modelling (FEM).

2 Snap-through using static piezoelectric actuation

The aim of this part is to present analytical, numerical and experimental previous results of the feasibility of switching a bistable system from one state to another using only piezoelectric static actuation. The principle of the analytical model is to replace the action of the PZ by two located moments at its extremities [7]. Numerical modelling of the PZ actuation of a bistable beam using one PZ patch (PZT material) was carried out using FEM software. Some positions optimising the snap-through voltage stood out. In particular, these points were tested experimentally for validation. The system and results are shown in Figure 1. $2R$ is a possible external force, P is the axial force for buckling

Fig. 1: Bistable beam under PZ actuation (left). Snap-through models curve with several experimentally validated points: snap-through voltage vs 1 PZ patch position (right)

and M models the PZ action. With the chosen initial deflection level ($D_0 = 1$ mm), the PZ actuator has indeed demonstrated its ability to switch a bistable buckled beam. This was proven for the steel beam of dimensions ($70 \times 14 \times 0.3$ mm³) with PZT ceramic of dimensions ($14 \times 14 \times 0.3$ mm³) glued on. An optimisation study was carried out to minimise the voltage required at snap-through as a function of the actuator position. The characteristic points of this study were verified experimentally (between 200 V and 280 V which is the maximum voltage supported by PZ actuators), and the errors were relatively small compared to the models.

3 Snap-through using dynamic actuation: FEM

The aim of this part is to present analytically and numerically the feasibility of snap-through and snap-back of a bistable structure using piezoelectric dynamic actuation. Figure 2 shows the design of the pre-buckled structure (midpoint deflection of 1 mm as showed in the bottom right graph at 0 Hz) with a PZ actuator perfectly bonded to its underside surface. A linear voltage chirp with amplitude 30 V is applied to get the

Fig. 2: Pre-buckled bistable structure actuated by a perfectly bonded PZ ceramic (left). Transverse displacement for a sweep on the PZ supply voltage frequency (right)

frequency response of the structure. The graph on the upper-right features two peaks indicating the instabilities which demonstrate the possibility, for this system dimensions and materials, of having snap-through and snap-back at two characteristic frequencies: $f_1 = 1170$ Hz and $f_2 = 1890$ Hz. This result will be tested experimentally in a future work and a theoretical study will address the frequencies for which the instability is triggered. If confirmed, these preliminary open the way to control the snap through and back thanks to the frequency with a reduced voltage.

Disclosure of Interests. The authors have no competing interests to declare that are relevant to the content of this article.

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